

Issues of Neighborhood (Makhalla) And Villages in Severe Conditions in The Aral Sea Region

AUTHOR(S): SEREYEVA GULJAZIRA ADILBAEVNA

Abstract

This paper describes and researches about Issues of Neighborhood (Makhalla) And Villages in Severe Conditions in The Aral Sea Region, Uzbekistan. The paper also outlines about improving the living conditions and quality of the population of the Aral Sea region, the State Program for the Development of the Aral Sea Region during the period, year from 2017 to 2021. Significantly the paper else provides information regarding ancient times, the castle wall and some gates of the city were open only at certain periods.

Keywords: Issues of Neighborhood (Makhalla), Villages in Severe Conditions, The Aral Sea Region, Uzbekistan,

IJARBAS

Accepted 10 June 2021

Published 16 June 2021

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4968800

About Author

Author(s):

SEREYEVA GULJAZIRA ADILBAEVNA

Tashkent Institute of Architecture and Construction,
Department of Urban Planning and Landscape Architecture,
Senior Lecturer, Uzbekistan.
E-mail: n.timur94@gmail.com

There is no doubt that the consequences of the ecological catastrophe caused by the drying up of the Aral Sea have already become a global problem, not only in Uzbekistan or the Central Asian region. The approach to the Aral Sea issue has changed radically in terms of achieving tangible results. Moreover, the head of our state twice drew the attention of the world community to this point from the UN rostrum.

Aimed at improving the living conditions and quality of the population of the Aral Sea region, the State Program for the Development of the Aral Sea Region for 2017-2021 has been approved. The UN Multilateral Human Security Partnership Trust Fund has been established for the Aral Sea region. The Aral Sea International Innovation Center was formed under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1]. In present days, the rapid development of socio-economic processes requires not only the looking for optimal ways to solve global dilemmas of mankind, but also the forming of issues such as the preservation of material and spiritual values and their transmission to future generations.

It is obvious from history that different forms of statehood and governance emerged during the long periods of human development. Their emergence, formation and development are not accidental, but are based on objective factors related to the socio-economic specificity of each period. Makhalla, guzar, interiors (dahis) and district are a unique form of self-government of the population, typical of the structure of cities and villages of Uzbekistan.

In ancient times, the castle walls and some gates of the city were open only at certain periods. Entrance fee was required. In the center of Asian cities was an area called Chorsu (four waters). In the square, the khan's decrees and the harsh decisions of the kazis (judges) against people who couldn't pay taxes, were read aloud. Festivals with intensive trade were held in the central squares. The streets leading to the city gates left the square. Between the streets were real labyrinths of small and narrow streets with many passages and dead spots.

The interiors (dahis) are thus formed between the main streets. Each interior had its own kazi (judge) and one commander (thousand people). The dahis were divided into neighborhood (makhalla) blocks and guzars (they were called ilot in Khiva). At the beginning of these dahis were the elders of the neighborhood. Thus, the neighborhood (makhalla) was the minimum administrative unit of the settlement. Tashkent is divided into 4 dahis (parts): Beshegoch, Kukcha, Sebzar and Shaykhantahur. These names can still be found on the city map. The number of neighborhoods (makhallas) was constantly changing. So, in the middle of the 19th century, there were 48 makhallas in Shaykhantahur, 38 in Sebzor, 32 in Beshegoch and 31 in Kukcha. For example, Okmasjid (White House) mahalla in Shayhantahur consisted of more than 400 houses, Chuvalachi mahalla in Sebzor (confusing? ...) consisted of more than 100 houses, and Beshegochni district of Samarkand Darbaza makhalla (Samarkand gate) contained 50 houses.

After some time, each neighborhood (makhalla) expands and splits into two or more smaller neighborhoods. In this continuous process flow, it was not always possible to maintain the production direction of the makhalla. Sometimes married couples were formed from young people living in different neighborhoods engaged in different crafts. Neighborhoods also emerged based on civic principles. Large neighborhoods grew from two or three families, which later came to be known by Tajik, Iranian, Jewish, and many other names.

There are distinctive traditions of the way of life of our nation formed over the centuries, mutual affection and other human relations, which are in line with the spirit of our nation.

Strengthening the material and spiritual basics of our country's development, preserving our national values, traditions and customs, especially instilling in the hearts and minds of the younger generation a deep love for the motherland, devotion to the basic ideas of national ideology emerge as a principal and practical matter. For a number of spiritual and educational activities organized to guide young people to the right path, to protect them from harmful habits, the influence of various alien ideas, to improve the spiritual environment in families, as well as such cultural facilities are crucial for the cultural recreation of the villagers [2]. However, unfortunately, existed and ready places are used uneffectively. Today, it is time to return to our people such cultural sites, which are now on the balance of cultural departments. This work has not been done on time, but also has been delayed.

From April 1, 2018 in each district and city of the country, first of all, in remote and difficult climatic conditions in 2018 in 2 and in the coming years in 3 villages (neighborhoods) to radically improve the living conditions of the population, lifestyle and level, to ensure significant positive changes, modernize the appearance of these villages (makhallas) and create jobs for their residents, the "Obod Qishloq" and "Obod Mahalla" programs will be implemented. The Republican Commission for Coordination of the Implementation of the Rural Development Program and its regional headquarters have compiled and approved a list of 368 villages to be developed in 2018.

Honestly, over the last 25 years, no practical work has been done to improve the appearance and beautification of the villages, except for the construction of exemplary housing, for which no funds have been allocated. In many villages, important areas such as streets, social facilities, drinking water, and electricity have been neglected and abandoned for years.

According to resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 11, 2020 "On measures for integrated socio-economic development of the Republic of Karakalpakstan in 2020-2023", a seminar was organized on the issues of effective implementation of the tasks on improving the living conditions of the population in difficult makhallas and auls and their removal from the heavy category through the beautification of the territories and strengthening the role and place of the mahalla in the Jogorku Kengesh of the Republic of Karakalpakstan on February 25, 2021.

The video conference was attended by members of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, deputies of the Jogorku Kengesh of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, government officials, heads of sectors and the media, as well as city and district council of people's deputies, heads of citizens' self-government bodies took part in city and district studios [1]. The resolution sets out an action plan to improve the living conditions of the population in 45 needy neighborhoods and auls, and about 20 areas for landscaping. According to the plan, 437 facilities will be built in difficult neighborhoods and auls, and a total of about 3 trillion soums will be allocated for its implementation.

In particular, construction and reconstruction of "Mahalla Markazlari" complexes in 12 district centers, construction of 157 makhalla and aul administrative complexes, construction of houses, roads, electricity, natural gas, drinking water supply, development of information and communication technologies, construction and reconstruction of social facilities, beautification in difficult makhallas and auls, as well as accelerated development of entrepreneurship, employment in these areas, also, important areas such as, the development of industry, agriculture, services are covered [3].

Nowadays, there are works such as laying gravel on roads, repairing bridges, as well as improving gas, electricity, heat supply, repairing and re-installing transformers, replacing

poles with concrete poles are being done in the mahallas and auls. Along with, the “Iron diary” (Temir daftar), “Women’s diary” (Ayollar daftari), and “Youth diary” (Yoshlar daftari), have been introduced to improve the living conditions of people living in difficult neighborhoods and auls, especially young people, to save their families from poverty by providing them with jobs and increasing their incomes.

During the event, the President visited some problematic makhallas in Fergana and Namangan regions, drew attention to the shortcomings and problems there, talked about the negligence of officials, and noted that such issues and shortcomings exist in some makhallas in our region and gave tasks to eliminate it have been identified [3].

It is vital to implement the new system set by the head of state, that is, to ensure that all the work and reforms are organized in a “neighborhood”, while ensuring the implementation of decisions taken by the head of state and the government in this process. Opinions and proposals were expressed on strengthening parliamentary control, increasing the activity of deputies of district (city) Councils of People's Deputies attached to areas with difficult socio-economic situation.

In our opinion, the development of a nation requires attention to every part of it. Each work done for the welfare of the country is a key factor in determining the future of the country, transforming it into a developed state. The Decree “*On the Rural Development Program*”, adopted on the initiative of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, is one of the factors determining our future. The program is aimed at radically reforming the lifestyle of the rural population, the introduction of infrastructure that does not differ from the urban environment, as well as changing the outlook of the rural population.

It is natural to ask why such a large program is planned in rural life. Every citizen of the country has a right to live in an urban environment that fully meets the requirements of the modern world, to enjoy all modern conditions, in general, to live a favourable and prosperous life. In particular, under this program, unplanned construction in remote areas was removed, and new ancillary buildings, trade and residential facilities were constructed.

Certainly, the makhallas and auls are the whole social structure in terms of architectural features, and these institutions must be preserved in any way. Libraries are being organized in makhallas and auls to attract young people to science and education. Surely, all this will have a positive effect on the growth of reading culture, the expansion of the intellectual and spiritual world of the younger generation. And reading is hard work, and the mind is free from clutter.

Naturally, the number of libraries and educational institutions in all regions and neighborhoods is growing. In each of his speeches, the head of our state emphasizes the education of young people, reading books, discovering and supporting talents. It encourages each of us to be vigilant, to take responsibility for our own lives, and to act as one.

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info@parliamentrk.gov.uz

Cite this article:

Author(s), SEREYEVA GULJAZIRA ADILBAEVNA, (2021). "Issues of Neighborhood (Makhalla) And Villages in Severe Conditions in The Aral Sea Region". **Name of the Journal:** International Journal of Academic Research in Business, Arts and Science, (IJARBAS.COM), P, 30- 35. **DOI:** <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4968800> Issue: 6, Vol.: 4, Article: 4, Month: June, Year: 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.ijarbas.com/all-issues/>

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